

**Philosophy of Language and Language
of Philosophy: Interrogation of
Prof. Okon Essien's Linguistic Perspectives**

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Abstract

Our concern in this paper is to highlight the main thrust of philosophy of language and to show why and how the language of philosophy has evolved over the years. The mystery of language in development, learning and propagation is a subject that needs interrogation. It is in this wise that we are anchoring our study on some of the contributions made by our erudite scholar Professor Okon Essien towards the development and better understanding of the dynamics and intricacies of language through linguistics which is the scientific study of language formation and development. In this paper we shall grapple with concepts like linguistics, language formation, theories of language, development of language, the scientific study of language, language generation and the postmodernization of language, psychologization of language and naturalization of language.

Keywords: Linguistics, Psycholinguistics, Phonology, Postmodernism, Deconstructionism, Naturalization, Psychology.

Résumé

Notre préoccupation dans cet article est de mettre en évidence les principaux axes de la philosophie de langue et de montrer pourquoi et comment la langue de la philosophie a évolué au fil des ans. Le mystère de la langue dans le développement, l'apprentissage et la propagation est un sujet qui a besoin d'être interrogé. C'est ainsi que nous ancrons notre étude sur certaines des contributions de notre érudit, le professeur Okon Essien, au développement et à une meilleure compréhension des dynamiques et des complexités de langue par la linguistique qui est l'étude scientifique de la formation et du développement des langues. Dans cet article, nous aborderons des concepts comme la linguistique, la formation linguistique, les théories de langue, le développement de la langue, l'étude scientifique de la langue, la génération de la langue et la postmodernisation de la langue, la psychologie de la langue et la naturalisation de la langue.

Mots-clés: Linguistique, Psycholinguistique, Phonologie, Postmodernisme, Déconstructivisme, Naturalisation, Psychologie

Introduction

Our interest in this work is to emphasize the importance of language and the ways and the wherefores of its linguistic analysis. Prof Okon Essien has done so much in situating the potency of language within the nexus of its mystical generative capacity. Anybody who has taken time to study the origin and development of English language and any other language for that matter will identify the following:

- (1) The very uncertain origin

- (2) The cause and limited confines of its beginning
- (3) The dynamic and refining capacity of language
- (4) The capacity of expansivity
- (5) The adaptive and accommodative nature of language in terms of borrowing and creation of new words in terms of neologisms
- (6) The self generative capacity of language – that is, the capacity for internal and external growth
- (7) The mystery of distinctiveness and provinciality of the phonology of different languages. The distinctiveness is extended to the syntax and semantic dimensions of language
- (8) The possibility of multilinguality without mixing codes of different languages. We also have the ease of translation; transliteration and switching over from one language to the other for those who are bilingual or multilingual.

In the study of the language of philosophy we have seen its adaptive, “incorporative”, generative and encyclopedic ambience in the course of development, we have moved from early Egyptian languages (writing of hieroglyphics), the Babylonians, the Syrians, the Assyrians, the Greeks, Romans, Germans, Hebrews (extending back to the Aramaic period) and English, French, Spanish and various indigenous languages.

Definition of Key Concepts

We shall examine the following concepts:

Language

Language is for me a communicative art between the hearer and the speaker. It is strings of words arranged syntactically and semantically for the sole purpose of communicating ideas, thoughts, moods, and for explaining action or inaction. Language is an art because it is theoretical, it is a skill, enjoin creativity and it is dynamic and generative. An art is something that borders on skill, creativity, originality, measures of imitation, novelty, dynamism. Language is expressive communicative, performative, referential, ideational, literary and informative. As Prof. Okon Essien would say, that language communication should be viewed in all its ramifications, for according to him, we use language not only positively to teach, explain, inform, direct, enlighten, praise, pray, please, etc, but also negatively to cheat, deceive, lie, mislead, misinform, misdirect, deride, insult, antagonize, etc (Essien, 2010). Language is therefore an enigmatic concept that needs to be studied inside out.

Linguistics

Linguistics according to Prof. Okon Essien is the scientific study of language as an entity or phenomenon through objective and rigorous analysis. Linguistics is said to be a science because it carries out its business through empirically verifiable observations and with reference to some general theory of language structure (18). The linguist though studies about language need not be a speaker of many languages (polyglot) but need to be equipped with the scientific tools that will enable the linguist to understand the structure of language. Linguistics is scientific because its method is science-based because of its inter-subjectivity, controllability and objectivity. Linguistics uses the method of observation, data collection,

data analysis, hypothesis, discrimination, identification of patterns, theorization and formulation of laws. Linguistics is divided into two theoretical and applied. The findings at the theoretical level are applied at the structural level for objective verdict.

Psycholinguistics

Psychology is important to us in the issue of language because it is concerned with that part of the human person that deals with ideas, thinking, thoughts, reasoning, consciousness, feeling, perception, memory, imagination, imitation, etc. The formation of language is an intricate nexus of related chain activities that are centred in the mind. This means that without 'mind' there will be no psychology and there will be no language. Psychology in its very deep and scientific study of the interconnectivity between thoughts and language has led to a branch of linguistics called psycholinguistics.

According to Prof. Okon Essien Psycholinguistics is defined as the study of language and mind (22). How is language formed? Is there a mechanism? Can this mechanism and dynamics be studied scientifically? The concern of psycholinguistics is to unravel the root connection between mind and language. Every language has its own grammar. Grammar is mentally represented as a system of rules and principles required and internalized (Okon Essien, 2010). This may lead to questions. Like, how do we acquire language? Is it by hereditary, imitation, learning, endowment, disposition, perception or induction? Truly there are aspects of the above involved in learning a language.

The myth of mother tongue which is transferred from parents to offspring is not completely true. There must be induction, imitation and learning for transmission of language to be possible. Philosophers like W.V.O. Quine (1969), P. F. Strawson (1971), Donald Davidson (1985), Noam Chomsky (1975) have taken time to talk about how we learn language. Quine in his *Ontological Relativity and Other Essays (1969)* highlighted how through imitation, induction, ostensive definitions we go bilingual or learn alien language or our mother tongue. He however points out that we have issues of indeterminacy of translation, opacity, inscrutability of reference etc, to contend with. But with painstaking mapping and learning through observation, imitation, ostensive definition and induction, it is possible to learn a language. This means that it is not automatic and it is not inherited. However, we may have the disposition to learn certain languages better than others (see my works of *Understanding the Philosophy of W.V.O. Quine, Introduction to Philosophy of Language and a Concise Introduction to Epistemology*). What we have established is that psychology is linked with linguistics in psycholinguistics.

Naturalization of Language

There has been this debate whether language is a natural outcome or an artificial contrivance. The question is whether language is naturally inculcated and transferred from parents to off-spring. Or is language an artificial meta-creation of human beings. The question cannot be answered in a straightforward manner. There is need to understand the intricacies of language development. However, this does not retract from the seeming truism that people tend to learn their mother tongue so effortlessly that a cursory perception might make look it just natural. But the truth is that all languages are learnt. However, people's facility to learn their mother tongue is enhanced because of

- (1) Nearness of and to speakers
- (2) Possibility of imitation and interaction
- (3) Possibility of repetition
- (4) Inculcation through ostensive definition
- (5) Higher capacity, disposition and learning towards mother tongue
- (6) The mystical phonological cum genetical endowments for mother tongue.

What we are saying, is that, the above dispose children to learn their mother tongue faster than an alien language. However, there is the artificial dimension to every language. Every language has its static and dynamic aspects. There are some basic components of language that have come to stay. For example, we have etymological meanings, we have standard syntactic and semantic meanings. On the other hand, we have other aspects that arise because of the generative capacity of the human mind captured in the possibility of neologisms. Here, we have new words and need linguistic development (Chomsky, 1975).

Issues in Philosophy of Language

There are many issues in the philosophy of language ranging from theories of language. There are the referential, ideational or behavioural to the intricacies in the postmodernization of language. The problems of reference as arising from opacity, ambiguity, inscrutability of reference, indeterminacy of meaning and reference, translation, to the problem of unfathomability of human mind and consciousness. How do we name an object? How do we cope with different names? For Bertrand Russell (1940), we have different names, but he sees all other names apart from those he classifies as logically proper names as misleading. This is because there are names that purport to name but name as nothing. If I say “The present king of Nigeria” – this is a name but names nobody. The question is, must names be single words like Caesar, Peter, Paul, James or phrases as in the case of the “present king of Nigeria?”.

This was what led the logical atomists spearheaded by Whitehead, Russell, Moore and Wittgenstein to emphasize the need for atomic sentences or what transmuted into picture theory of language. The idea was to have atomic names name atomic objects and compound names name compound objects. How do we contend with the problem of multiple references or multiple names referring to the same thing. Morning Star and Evening Star were later discovered to refer to the same object Venus. The name Caesar can refer to many individuals that bear the name. This led Wittgenstein to abandon his picture theory of language to embrace what he calls the use theory of language in his *Philosophical Investigations* which is a departure from his position in *Tractatus Logico Philosophicus*.

Apart from the above, we have the problem of abstraction. George Berkeley dwelt so much on the evil of abstractions in his *Principles of Human Knowledge* (1662). How do we formulate abstract language from concrete objects? Names should refer to objects, and events, they should be led together by grammatical connectives or what Nelson Goodman (1972) calls syncategorematic words like ‘is’, but ‘whether’, ‘thought’, etc. How do we move from concrete man to abstract generic “man” that embraces male and female? There is an element of deception, misrepresentation and falsehood. We cannot talk about things that are singular in pluralistic terms. Things that are “gendered” should be captured under appropriate concepts.

Another problem is how do we determine the scope of concepts? A particular concept may be capable of multiple exemplifications and diverse instantiations. Its scope and limits may be as elastic as human ingenuity may allow. The concept of motion, mass, velocity are all fraught with the difficulty of definite instantiation.

We have other issues like problem of descriptions, perception, speech acts, private language, determination of truth through language, the problem of identity and necessity, the problem of identity of indiscernibles. The problem of ordinary language and technical language, the problem of ideal language and the problem of postmodernism, and deconstructionism in language (see Ozumba's *Introduction to Philosophy of Language*).

We must note that language as a human and non-instinctive method of communicating ideas, feelings and desires, by a system of signs, symbols, cannot be systematized with finality. It must continue to grow as man grows in knowledge and discovery.

Development of Language of Philosophy

The language of philosophy has passed through the crucible of refinement and counter refinement. It has suffered reversals in some epochs and renaissance in some periods. It has been buffeted and censored at various periods. However, we must stress that the ingenuity of philosophers arose through the ingenuity of their use of language.

From the ancient period philosophers like Thales, Anaximander, Anaximenes, Xenophanes, Empedocles, Anaxagoras, Heraclitus, Parmenides, Zeno, Pythagoras, Sophists, Socrates, Plato, Aristotle, and others remain the icons that initiated us into the arts and mysteries of philosophical language. They introduced into philosophy important concepts like the 'urstuff', the indeterminate, the concept of water, air, earth and fire, as the basic stuff of the universe the unlimited, the idea of flux, 'plenum' etc. Socrates, Plato and Aristotle can be named as giving us the largest quantum of philosophical words, in the ancient periods. We have words, like the "unexamined life", "dialectics", "world of forms", "potentiality" and "actuality", "categories", concept, "general" politics, "philosopher king" the unmoved mover, the uncaused cause, causal sui, sui generis, etc.

During the medieval period, we have St. Augustine, Thomas Aquinas, St. Anselm, Ockham, St. Bonaventure, Sextus Empiricus and many others. We have inundation of philosophical words that later dead the Ire of the logical positivists. Such words and phrases like "the chariots of fire", "the flying horse", the Union of spirits", "trinity". "Immanence and transcendence", "abstraction" etc. This led David Hume, one of the notable empiricist philosophers to say "when we run over libraries, persuaded of these principles, what havoc must we make? If we take in our hand any volume of divinity or school metaphysics, for instance, let us ask, does it contain any abstract reasoning, concerning matter of fact or existence. No. Commit it then to the flames, for it can contain nothing but sophistry and illusion" (Stumpf, 1975).

The use of metaphysical jargons became rife at this time, Abstraction and endless imaginative creations became the order of the day. The use of high-sounding words, metaphysical words without physicalistic grounding was the way of demarcating the learned from the unlearned. This led William Ockham to propose his Ockham's razor emphasizing by it that entities should not be multiplied beyond what is necessary (entia non sunt

multiplicand praeter necessitatem). Francis Bacon followed up by denouncing all Aristotelian and scholastic jargons as constituting idols and fantastical forms of learning lacking in scientific credibility. The logical positivists branded all metaphysical statements as nonsensical and meaningless.

In the modern period we have the rationalist and empiricist philosophers, like Rene, Descartes, Spinoza, Leibniz, John Locke, George Berkeley and David Hume. Though they tried to pursue precision in their use of language, they still suffered slips and pitfalls. Descartes talked about the incorporate Corporate and Incorporate Substances

Spinoza talked about 'Deus sive natura', pantheism and the idea of substance. Leibniz introduced the concept of Monadism and occasionalism. John Locke pushed farther the use of concepts of substance which he says is "a thing he knows not what" and the concept of abstraction. For Berkeley, we have the concept of immaterialism, heuristics, idea, finite and infinite mind, etc. David Hume, the advocate of linguistic purity himself introduced the concept of "impressions". "Cause and effect", etc.

In the contemporary period we have several developments leading to great proliferation of philosophical words and further enriching of the language of philosophy and extending the frontiers of knowledge. We have come to identify that the frontiers of language is the scope of knowledge. It is language that determines the extent of our knowledge. No wonder Wittgenstein said that the whereof we cannot speak thereof we must remain silent. The generation of language tantamounts to the development of knowledge.

The language of confusion, obfuscation, inexactitude and misrepresentations have become the concomitant side effects of unbridled creation of words by humans. In the contemporary period we have concepts like existentialism, phenomenology, pragmatism, vitalism, naturalized epistemology, reliabilism, feminism, artificial intelligence, neo structuralism, non-foundationalism, neo-cognitivism, constructionism, etc.

In the postmodern period, language development attained its most bizarre and anarchistic nadir in the history of language formation. After the Second World War with the aftermath of depression, despair, frustration, individualism, secularism, irrationalism, survival syndrome, pessimism, anomie, subjectivism, relativism, postmodernism, came on board to articulate and encapsulate all the extremes of Marxism, anarchism, nihilism. Postmodernism is antithetical to modernism, kicks against metanarratives, grand totalizing of idea, standard foundationalism, rationality, status quo, objectivity, consensus and prescriptivism, fetishism. It has injured clarity in language more than all other developments in philosophy – with its audacious and provocative genre and monumental authoritarianism of discursive exercises with outlandish linguistic styles.

In this present period, I have introduced what is called the period of integrative humanism with its peculiar linguistic repertoire. We have coined such words as eclecticism, agglutinism, spiritcentricism, integrativism, humanocentrism, mundanocentrism, etc.

Like Hegel was known as a metaphysical words-spinner so are philosophers' stock in trade the creation of new words to capture new ideas. Philosophers have remained faithful to this project and no amount of censorship will hinder philosophers and this task of increasing the frontiers of knowledge through progressive manufacture of new words. New ideas must be captured with new words. Today, in philosophy of science we have moved from Newtonian ontology of macrophysics to Einsteinian ontology of microphysics. We are now

talking about quanta, quarks, mesons, lepton, fuzzy logic, hadrons and theory of everything.

Lessons from Prof. Okon Essien

Prof. Okon Essien's work titled *Commissioned and Inspired Vital Aspects of Linguistics* is a compendium of great ideas of linguistics. It lays bare all we need to know about linguistics, psycholinguistics, developmental linguistics, and neurolinguistics. He has also taken time to explain why there is power in the spoken word in line with the Holy Writ. Speech as he says quoting Publicus is the "mirror of the soul". Speech is used in argumentation, persuasion, propaganda.

He has also through the scientific analyses of Nigerian languages shown that all Nigerian languages have much in common since they belong to the Niger-Congo Family – now referred to as New Benue Congo Family (2010). He has shown how the different languages in Nigeria developed. Language is also depicted as the mirror of culture. He has worked on the phonology, syntax and semantics of languages.

His in-depth study of Noam Chomsky's work led him to the biological origin of words and biology as the basis for language acquisition. He delved into African linguistics and showed the analysis of the root and branches and derivation of word and the etymologies of African words and their interethnic linkages. Our eyes have indeed been opened to the rich inquiry we can be opened to if we can painstakingly pursue the anatomical study of African language. We can discover similarities and reasons for harmony, unity and friendliness across the continent.

Conclusion

We have come a long way and have successfully shown what language is, what linguistics is, the role psychology plays in language development. We have also seen the development of the language of philosophy and the philosophy of language. We have cemented all with our lessons from Prof Okon Essien's discourses in linguistics. The study of language from Prof. Okon Essien's contributions to linguistics can no longer be approached with a cavalier, non-enthusiastic attitude. Good grasp of our language can give us access to power and the force of authority that is inherent in spoken word. In all, it has been a rewarding study that has opened our eyes to hitherto hidden truth.

Language of philosophy is characterized by physicalism, abstraction, creation, innovation, imagination and metaphysics. We have such important metaphysical terms like being, non-being, becoming, ontology, substance, equality, actuality, potentiality, universals, particulars, individuation, identity, indiscernible, necessity, essentialism, existentialism, facticity, etc. In ethics we are talking about morality, deontologism, teleologism, intuitionism, emotivism, situationism, utilitarianism, hedonism, freewillism, determinism, naturalism, non-naturalism, relativism, Epicureanism, stoicism, altruism, egoism. In epistemology we have foundationalism, non-foundationalism, cognitivism, constructionism, solipsism, realism, idealism, phenomenism, coherentism, pragmatism, empiricism, rationalism, skepticism, rationalism, structuralism, vitalism, naturalization, psychologization, scientism, reliabilism, internalism, externalism, feminism, virtue, epistemology, geneticism, evolutionism, integrationism, etc. In other areas of philosophy different terms have been coined and are in use. This is a continuing exercise in philosophy.

Proliferation of words, terms, concepts and phrases are part of the main business of the philosopher. He is called to enrich the linguistic repertoire for cognitive discourse. The issue of language is therefore very critical for the development of philosophy of language. Therefore, it is not out of place to say that the development of language means the development of the philosophy of language and the development of the philosophy of language means the development of the language of philosophy and philosophy itself as a discipline that thrives on language.

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